

Status Analysis of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidayala (KGBV) in Ganjam District

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ABSTRACT

Health and education are two major pillars of development. Education is the catalyst factor which leads to economic development and promotes quality of life, comparing better health, nutrition, improved sociology economic opportunities and more congenial and beneficial natural environment to all. The national policy on education 1986 intended to bring change in a missionary zeal to improve girl's education through residential schooling facilities. Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidayala (KGBV) is an institutional development intervention started in 2004 to impart quality education for girls between 10-14 years belonging to SC, ST, OBC and Minority communities and families below poverty line (BPL) in educationally back ward blocks with boarding facilities at elementary level.

The present piece of research based on explanatory design intended to cover its universe through stratified purposive random sample survey on kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidayala in five blocks of Ganjam district.

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KEYWORDS: Girls, education, health

India is one of the largest democratic country in the world. It has a systematic education system which has a huge demand. But after 67 years of independence of India we are away from the goal of universal literacy. Till now, SC/ST/Woman rural people etc. are considered as deprived social group of our society in every side. They are suffering from a lot of problems and cannot go ahead of course. Government of India be either announces many welfare schemes for weaker section of our society time to time. These schemes could be either central, state specific or a joint collaboration between centre and state.

Looking at the enrolment level in elementary as well as appear primary classes and the retention in. Significant gaps at the elementary level still persist in rural as well as level as well as among disadvantages communities in upper primary level. However, the Government of India has introduced a Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) scheme for setting up residential schools with all facilities at elementary level for girls belonging predominantly to Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe, Other Backward Class and Minority Community with the objectives to ensure equal opportunity and to improve barrier free environment to girls. The Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) scheme was launched by the Government of India in August 2004 for setting up residential schools at upper primary level for girls belonging predominantly to the SC, ST, OBC and Minorities in

the difficult areas. KGBV scheme provides for a minimum reservation of 75% of the seats for girls belong to SC, ST, OBC or Minority Communities and priority for the remaining 25% is accorded to girls from families Below Poverty Line (BPL). KGBV run as a separate scheme but in harmony with the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA). SSA is Government of India's flagship programme for achievement of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) in a time bound manner making free and compulsory education to the children of 6 – 14 years age group. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) has a special focus on girl's education and children with special needs. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) also seeks to provide computer education to bridge the digital divide.

Since its Educationally Backward Blocks (EBBs), where the rural female literacy is below national average (46.13% Census 2001) and gender in literacy is more than the national average (21.59% Census 2001) among blocks.

In the context of above scenario this paper is an attempt to analyse the status of KGBV in different blocks of Orissa state. Thus the objective of the study are formulated as :

1. To study the enrolment status of the KGBV in selected blocks of Ganjam district.
2. To know the infrastructure and facilities of KGBV.
3. To understand the life style of hostel dwellers of (KGBV) students in Ganjam district.

- To study food consumption pattern of students of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya(KGBV) .
- To assess various facilities provided to the students of KGBV in the hostel.
- To study about vocational training provided to the students of KGBV.
- To know the views of students of KGBV regarding their problems and their suggestion for betterment of KGBV.

Need of the study:

Directive principle of state policy through Article 45 states that the state should provide free and compulsory education to all children of age of 14. Article 46 of our constitution states to promote the educational need of weaker sections of the society(SC, ST, OBC). As per this constitutional obligations through national policy of education various steps are taken for the girls education in our state. A number of centrally sponsored scheme are being continued, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) is one of them for improve girl child education of SC, ST, OBC, BPL and educationally backward classes. The main aim of study is to know about educational facilities and problems of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) hostel students in Ganjam district.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

There are 17 KGBV in Ganjam district of Odisha state out of which the researcher has selected five number of blocks . Thus the scope of this study has been confined to Kukudakhandi block, Hinjilicut block of Gopinathpur, Chhatrapur block of Rickapalli, Chikiti block of Ramachandrapur, Digapahandi block of Padmanavpur of Ganjam district. 100 number of samples selected from each Kasturba Gandhi Vidyalaka (KGBV) randomly for the purpose of the study.

METHODOLOGY:

Tools and Techniques used:

In the present study primary data have been used. The researcher had prepared a set of questionnaire and open interview schedule to collect data further students of KGBV. The interviewing had later gone through a pilot study and the modification were being done looking in view the objects of the study.

The researcher had picked up 500 number of samples randomly for the present study. The samples were chosen from all the categories of SC,ST,OBC and BPL students of five blocks ofKasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) of

Ganjam district. From each school 100 number of samples were picked up randomly for be purpose.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION: -

Researcher had selected five Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) randomly from selected five blocks of Ganjam district. The researcher went for collection of data after obtaining formal permission from the Block Education Officer (BEO)/ Headmaster / Headmistress of different KGBV of Ganjam district and visited selected KGBV of Ganjam district during August and September,2014 for collection of data. The researcher personally met the students of KGBVs five blocks. Researcher also met Headmaster/Headmistress and teachers for collection of information through questionnaire. Researcher prepared questionnaire for the sample groups. The researcher conducted a pilot study and modified the questionnaire as required.

The researcher fastor interested with the Headmaster/Headmistress and collected infomation by using questionare. The questionare comprises two parts, first part is connected with school profile and the second set of schedule is with regard to various facilities, services and problems of KGBVs. Researcher talked with the samples and interacted with them about by using questionnaire method and personal interview method regarding various facilities provided by Central Government and different problems faced by them in the hostel. After collection of data the researcher compiled the data and analysed the information by using numerical and percentage statistical method.

Result Analysis:

The data collected by the researcher has been analyzed under the following sub headings:

Enrolment status:

Table No. 1 shows student strength of different classes of KGBV of all five blocks. The data in the table reflects that in class 6th there were 8 number of students, in 7th class 39 number of students and in 8th class 53 number of students were enrolled in the year 2014 in Kukudakhandi block. In Hinjili block of Gopinathpur KGBV 30 number of students in 6th class, in 7th class 34 number of students and in 8th class 36 number of students were studying. In Chhatrapur block of Rickapalli. in 6th class 31 number of students, in 7th class 29 number of students and in 8th class 40 number of students were enrolled.

Table No. 1

Enrolment Status in KGBV (Block wise)

Sl. No.	Name of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) (Block wise)	VI	VII	VIII	Total
1	Kukudakhandi	8	39	53	100
2	Hinjili	30	34	36	100
3	Chhatrapur	31	29	40	100
4	Digapahandi	4	44	52	100
5	Chikiti	29	46	25	100
Total		102 (20.4%)	192 (38.4%)	206 (41.2%)	500 (100%)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage)

In Digapahandi block of Padmanavpur Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) 100 number of students were enrolled. In 6th class 4 number of students, in 7th class 46 number of students and in 8th class 52 number of students were enrolled. In Chikiti block of Ramachandrapur Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) 100 number of students were enrolled where in 6th class 29 number of students, in 7th class 46 number of students and in 8th class 25 number of students were studying. In all the KGBV of five blocks of total number of students were 500 where in 6th class 102 (20.4%) number of students, in 7th class 192 (38.4%) number of students and in 8th class 206(41.2%) number of students were enrolled.

Table No. 2 shows in Kukudakhandi KGBV there were 22 (22%) number of dropout students enrolled in 6th class and 2 (2%) number of dropout students enrolled in Ramachadrapur KGBV in class 6th, thus 24 (4.8%) number of dropout students were enrolled

Table No. 2 Enrolment Status of Dropout Students in KGBV(Block wise)

Sl. No.	Name of the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) (Block wise)	No. of Students (%)
1	Kukudakhandi	22 (22%)
2	Hinjili	-
3	Chhatrapur	-
4	Digapahandi	-
5	Chikiti	2 (2%)
	Total	24 (4.8%)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentage)

FOOD PATTERN IN THE HOSTEL:

Table No. 3 shows that their early morning breakfast used to be 6 pieces of biscuits from Sunday to Saturday, all holidays, festivals between 6.30 AM to 7AM. The students used to take school mid-day meal as their lunch from Monday to Saturday between 1 PM to 1.30 PM. A little variation was found on holidays and festivals for breakfast, lunch, evening tiffin and dinner. On Sunday breakfast they took suji halwa and banana between 9AM to 9.30AM.

Table-3 Weekly Menu of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV)

Day	Early morning breakfast 6.30 to 7 AM	Breakfast 9AM to 9.30AM	Lunch 1PM to 1.30PM	Evening Tiffin 5.30PM to 6PM	Dinner 9PM to 9.30PM
Sunday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Suji Halwa, Banana	Rice, dal, chicken curry for vegetarian paneer, salad	Puffed rice mixture	Rice/roti, dalma, potherb bhaja (sago)
Monday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Suji Upama, Dalma	School mid- day meal	Sprouted moong, sugar, zaggry	Rice/roti, soyabin curry, bhaja, pickle
Tuesday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Sattu, Ragi, Milk	School mid- day meal	Semiya kheer	Rice/roti, rajama curry/todaka, bhaja, pickle
Wednesday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Chuda upama, Dalma	School mid- day meal	Chick-boiled (buto)	Rice/roti, egg curry, veg pamapada, pickle
Thursday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Hotch potch of rice and spices (Khichidi) Curry, pickle	School mid- day meal	Pea-boil	Rice, drumstick curry, patato, brinje, cakes of pasted pluse, (bodi) pickle, pampada
Friday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Idle, Pea Curry	School mid- day meal	Pokoda	Rice/roti, chlick (Buto) curry, pickle
Saturday	Biscuit 6 Piece	Puri, Patato curry	School mid- day meal	Chat, Pea-curry Onion, pampada	Rice, fish curry, basan curry, chips, salad
Holidays & Festivals	Biscuit 6 Piece	Puri, Patato curry, sweets	Rice, dal, chicken curry for vegetarian paneer, salad	Chick-boiled (Buto)	Parata, Dalma, Milk

They took their lunch between 1PM to 1.30PM. Sunday lunch included rice, dal, chicken curry, for vegetarian they were given paneer curry and salad. They took puffed rice mixture as evening tiffin between 5.30PM to 6PM on Sunday. Sunday dinner included rice, dal/roti, dalma, potherb (sago) bhaja between 9PM to 9.30PM. The students of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) used to take mid-day meal as their lunch from Monday to Saturday between 1 PM to 1.30PM. Monday's breakfast was suji upama and dalma. They were taking sprouted moong dal with sugar /jaggry as Monday evening tiffin between 5.30 PM to 6 PM. They were taking rice/roti, soyabin curry, bhaja, pickle as dinner between 9PM to 9.30PM on Monday. On Tuesday they had sattu, ragi and milk as their breakfast between 9AM to 9.30 AM. They had semiya kheer as evening tiffin between 5.30 PM to 6PM. Tuesday dinner included rice, roti, rajama curry, tadoka and pickle between 9PM to 9.30PM. On Wednesday they were taking chuda upama and dalma between 9AM to 9.30AM as their breakfast. They ate boiled pea (buto) as evening tiffin between 5.30 PM to 6PM. In dinner they were taking rice/roti, egg curry for vegetarian pickle and pampada between 9PM to 9.30PM on Wednesday. On Thursday they had hotch potch of rice and spieces (Khichidi) patato curry and pickle as their breakfast between 9AM to 9.30 AM. They were taking peas (boiled) as evening tiffin between 5.30PM to 6Pm. In dinner rice, drumstick curry, patato, brinje, cakes of pasted rice (bodi) pickle and pampada were served between 9PM to 9.30PM on Thursday. On Friday they were taking Idli, Pea curry as their breakfast between 9AM to 9.30AM, they took pokoda as their evening tiffin between 5.30PM to 6PM, and in dinner rice/roti, chick (buto) curry, pickle were served between 9PM to 9.30PM on Friday. On Saturday they ate puri, patato curry as their breakfast. They ate chat-pea curry, onion, pampada as their evening tiffin. They in dinner rice, fish curry, basan curry, chips and salad were served between 9PM to 9.30PM on Saturday. On holidays and festivals

days puri, potato and sweets as were served their breakfast. They were taking rice, dal, paneer curry, salad, pampada, and khata as lunch between 1PM to 1.30PM, on holidays and festivals. They were eating chick (buto) boiled as their evening tiffin. In dinner dinner paratha, dalma and milk were served between 9PM to 9.30PM on holidays and festivals.

PATTERN OF LIVING:

Table No.4 shows the pattern of living style from Monday to Friday in a week. The students used to get up from bed around 5 AM in the morning and they finished their daily routine between 6AM. Thereafter they used to attend prayer, drill and yoga till 6.30 AM. After 6.30AM they were attending gardening and school cleaning work (up to 7AM). Thereafter they had remedial teaching classes taken by part time teachers from 7AM to 9AM and they take their breakfast from 9AM to 9.30AM. During 9.30 AM to 10 AM they used to get ready to go to school. They used to remain in the school from 10AM to 1PM and were attending their classes as per time table. They used to take their lunch between 1 PM to 1.30 PM. After lunch again they were attending classes up to 4 PM. They took rest from 4 PM to 4.30 PM in the hostel. From 4.30 PM to 5.30 PM they used to pray. Again they had their prayer and then they read newspaper till 6.30 PM. Again they used to attend

Table no-4 (KGBV) (Monday to Friday)

Morning		Afternoon		Evening	
5AM to 6AM	Daily work	10AM to 1PM	school hours study	4.30PM to 5.30PM	Playing
6AM to 6.30AM	Prayer, Drill, Yoga	1PM to 1.30PM	Lunch Break	5.30PM to 6.30PM	Prayer, reading newspaper
6.30AM to 7AM	Gardening, School clean	1.30PM to 4 PM	school hours study	6.30PM to 7.30PM	Life skill training
7AM to 9AM	Remedial teaching by part time teacher	4PM to 4.30 PM	Rest	7.30PM to 8.30PM	Remedial teaching by part time teacher
9AM to 9.30AM	Breakfast			8.30PM to 9.30PM	Watching T.V.
9.30AM to 10AM	Ready for school			9.30PM to 10PM	Dinner
				10PM	Go to bed

life skill training class from 6.30PM to 7.30PM. From 7.30 PM to 8.30 PM they used to attend remedial teaching classes taken by part time teachers. After classes were over they used to watch television programmes from 8.30 PM to 9.30 PM. They finished their dinner between 10PM and thereafter they had their rest and sleep.

Table No.5 shows the pattern of living of Saturday. There was a little bit difference in programme of Saturday. On Saturday as usual they used to get up and finished their daily work between 5AM to 6AM. They attend prayer, yoga and drill between 6AM to 6.30 AM.

Table no- 5 Pattern of Living of Saturday of KGBV

Morning		Afternoon		Evening	
5AM to 6AM	Daily work	10AM to 1PM	school hours study	5.30PM to 6.30PM	Prayer, reading newspaper
6AM to 6.30AM	Prayer, Drill, Yoga	1PM to 1.30PM	Rest	6.30PM to 8PM	Learning different song, dance, drawing
6.30AM to 7AM	Ready for school, breakfast	1.30PM to 4 PM	Gardening	8PM to 9PM	Remedial teaching by part time teacher
7AM to 11AM	school hours study	4PM to 4.30 PM	Vocational training	9PM to 9.30PM	Watching T.V.
				9.30PM to 10PM	Dinner
				10PM	Go to bed

As on Saturday there was morning classes, they used to get themselves ready for school and had breakfast between 6.30 AM to 7AM. From 7AM to till 11 AM they were in the school, they took rest from 11AM to 3PM. They were doing gardening work from 3PM to 4PM. Thereafter had their prayer, read newspaper during 5.30PM to 6.30PM, from 6.30PM to 8PM they were attending different extracurricular activities such as dance, song and drawing. They attend remedial teaching classes from 8PM to 9PM. They used to take dinner between 9.30PM to 10PM. After dinner they used to go to bed at 10PM.

Table No.6 shows the pattern of living on Sunday in Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV).

Table-6 Pattern of Living of Sunday of KGBV

Morning		Afternoon		Evening	
5AM to 9AM	Daily work, school boundary and clean room, breakfast	11AM to 1PM	Vocational Training	6PM to 6.30PM	Prayer, reading newspaper
9AM to 11AM	Health Checkup	1PM to 1.30PM	Meeting with parents	6.30PM to 7PM	Student union
		4 PM	Rest	7PM to 9PM	Film show
		4PM to 4.30 PM	Life skill training	10PM	Dinner and Sleep

On Sunday students of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) had their daily morning work between 5AM to 9AM. Thereafter they used to clean school boundary and school class room, then they used to take their breakfast. After breakfast they went health-checkup programme up to 11AM. They had vocational training programme from 11AM to 1PM. From 1 PM to 3PM they were meeting their parents who had come from their villages. The students used to take rest from 3PM to 4PM. They were attending life skill training in the hostel from 4PM to 5PM. They were attending prayer and read newspaper from 6PM to 6.30PM. They took part in discussion of student union between 6.30 PM to 7.30 PM. Thereafter they were watching film show from 7PM to 9PM. After film show they had their dinner and at 10.PM they had their night sleep.

FACILITIES:

Table No. 7 shows various facilities provided to Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) students. All the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) are provided with facilities of water, electricity, toilet, television, newspaper, warden, peon, watchman, teaching aid, holidays and vacations, telephone, kitchen room, playground, observation festival, scholarship, savings bank account, picnic, examination, vocational training, library, health-check-up, extra-curricular activities, meeting with parents, study material, note book, computer laboratory, all necessary of adolescent girls, play

Table no-7 Facilities Provided in Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV)

Facilities	Name of the Block									
	Kukudakhandi		Hinjili		Chhatrapur		Digapahandi		Chikiti	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Water supply	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Electricity	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Toilet	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Television	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Newspaper	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Warden	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Peon	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Watchman	Yes		Yes		Yes			No	Yes	
Teaching aid	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Holiday and vacation	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Uniform	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Telephone	Yes		Yes			No	Yes		Yes	
Kitchen room	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Mid day meal	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Proper food	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Observation festival	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Scholarship	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Savings bank a/c	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Picnic	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Examination	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Playground	Yes		Yes			No	Yes		Yes	
Vocational training	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Library	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Health Checkup	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Extracurricular activities	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Meeting with parents	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Study material	Name of the Block		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	

Facilities	Kukudakhandi									
	Yes		Hinjili		Chhatrapur		Digapahandi		Chikiti	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Note book	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Computer Lab	Yes			No	Yes		Yes		Yes	
All necessities of adolescent girl	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Play equipments	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
School bag, pen, pencil	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Umbrella	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Shoes, Soap	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Scale	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Sampoo, Comb, hair oil			Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Reading Room				No		No		No	Yes	

equipments and personal articles like school bag, pen, pencils, umbrella, shoes, scale, comb, soap, hair oil and reading room. Gopinathpur KGBV of Hinjili block had no computer laboratory facilities for the students. Rickapalli KGBV of Chhatrapur block was no telephone, reading room, playground facilities to the students. Except in Ramchandrapur KGBV of Chikiti block all other four KGBV had no reading room facilities to the students.

The most motivating facility provided in KGBV for the students was opening savings bank account for each students where Rs.50/- per month was deposited for them from class VI to VIII. Similar findings have been reported in the study of Baruah (2013) in Assam and Das (2013)

VOCATIONAL TRAINING:

Table No.8 shows in Kukudakhandi Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) researcher had taken 100 number of students as sample group. Only 40 number of students were taking up dance training, 30 number of students were learning songs and 30 number of students were undergoing tailoring training. In Hinjili block of Gopinathpur Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) researcher had taken 100 number of students as sample group. 50 number of students were taking up dance training, 30 number of students were learning songs, 10 number of students were undergoing tailoring training and 10 number of students were undergoing knitting training.

Table no-8 Samples Undergoing Vocational Training Programme in KGBV (Block wise)

Sl. No.	Name (of KGBV) (Block wise)	Dance	Song	Tailor	Embroidery	Knitting	Students
		Number of Samples					Total Number of Samples
1	Kukudakhandi	40	30	30	-	-	100
2	Hinjili	50	30	10	-	10	100
3	Chhatrapur	40	20	30	-	10	100
4	Digapahandi	50	30	20	-	-	100
5	Chikiti	50	50	-	-	-	100
Total		230 (46%)	160 (32%)	90 (18%)	-	20 (4%)	500

((Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage))

In Chhatrapur block of Rickapalli KGBV out of 100 students researcher had taken 100 number of students as sample group. 40 number of students were taking up dance training, 20 number of students were learning songs, 30 number of students were undergoing tailoring training and 10 number of students were undergoing knitting training. In Digapahandi block of Padmanavpur KGBV researcher had taken 100 number of students as sample group. 50 number of students were taking up dance training, 30 number of students were learning songs and 20 number of students were undergoing tailoring training. In Chikiti block of Ramachandrapur(KGBV) researcher had taken of 100 number of students as sample group where 50 number of students were taking up dance training, 50 number of students were learning songs. In all five blocks of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) in Ganjam district 46 (46%) number of students were learning dance training, 32 (32%) number of students were learning songs, 18(18%) number of samples were undergoing tailoring training and 4(4%) number of students were undergoing knitting training.

Participation of selected students in vocational training programmes of KGBV (Table no. 7) was satisfactory. The result shows that there were 46% of students taking up dance training, 32% of students were learning songs, 18% of students were undergoing tailoring training and 4% of students were undergoing knitting training. Similar findings were stated by Brhama (2012), Pradhan (2012) and Mishra (2012).

MAJOR FINDINGS:

1. Enrolment status of selected KGBV of five blocks were according to the guidelines but enrolment number of SC, ST, OBC, Minority Communities and BPL students were not according to guideline.
2. There were no dropout students in selected KGBV of five blocks during the year 2014. On the other hand dropout students other than the KGBV were enrolled in Ramachandrapur KGBV and Kukudakhandi KGBV.
3. The students of KGBV were attending various vocational training programmes.
4. The students of five KGBV were provided with food facilities as per menu.
5. The pattern of living facilities were as per chart provided by the Government.

CONCLUSION:

The KGBV is meant for the improvement of education of SC, ST, OBC, BPL and Minority. It is the best facilities for the educationally backward students by the Government. KGBV residential school is to ensure access to quality education and to reduce the dropout and over aged girls of society. KGBV is a small school serving 100 girls but its reach however is far and wide. The vast majority of students at KGBV school are the first generation to be educated in their family.

In the present study the result and observation of the study show that the enrolment students of KGBV was more than satisfactory in case of SC,ST and OBC, but so far as BPL category was concerned the enrolment status was not up to the guideline. Various educational facilities like study material, class room teaching and toilet facilities were provided to all the KGBV. The students of KGBV were provided with different vocational training programmes like dance, song and tailoring. And residential facilities were also provided all the boarders of the hostel as per provision. But in few KGBV there were lack of separate classroom, library, playground, boundary wall, drinking water, watchmen and telephonic communication. It was also observed that all the KGBV students were found to be disciplined, cheerful, clean and well manner. To conclude it can be stated that even though all the KGBVs were functioning successfully, in some of the KGBVs problems were lying which should be properly monitored and taken care of for the better performance of KGBVs.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- [1] Provision should made by the Government for their higher education and better placement.
- [2] The KGBVs should have only women staff in different positions and responsibilities like head for the institution ,teachers,office staff,warden and cooks.

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